
When Standard MI Tools Break: Chain Property Failures and Probe-Delta Dissociation in Hybrid Physics-ML Architectures

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Abstract

We document two failure modes of standard mechanistic interpretability tools in hybrid physics-ML architectures, using a gravitational lens classifier as a controlled testbed. **(1) Chain property:** interchange interventions yield structurally identical logit deltas at every classification head hook in all three models tested, making head-level routing/collapse verdicts structurally uninformative. The triggering condition—deterministic eval-mode sequential subgraphs—is identified precisely, instantiating [Mueller et al. \(2024\)](#)’s theoretical non-transitivity result. **(2) Probe-delta dissociation:** at the Poisson layer, D4LensPINN and a non-equivariant control show $3.6\times$ different causal sensitivity (bootstrap 95% CIs non-overlapping: 0.402 vs. 1.429), yet near-identical group-element probe accuracy (0.485 vs. 0.479). Equivariance reshapes causal sensitivity without reshaping representational content. Spectral analysis identifies the mechanism: the Poisson $1/k^2$ operator empirically collapses 59.5% mid-frequency orbit variance at D4’s $\hat{\kappa}$ to near-zero (VanillaLensPINN: identical operator, $\delta_{H09}=1.43$). These findings apply to any architecture with deterministic physics operators or eval-mode fixed normalizations.

1. Introduction

Interchange interventions ([Meng et al., 2022](#); [Wang et al., 2023](#)) and linear probing are the two workhorses of mechanistic interpretability. They are often treated as measuring the same thing: *where is information causally live?* We show empirically that they can give orthogonal answers at the same layer, and that interchange interventions fail structurally on a broadly applicable class of architectures.

D4LensPINN provides three MI-relevant properties: (a)

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algebraic D4 symmetry boundary at a known layer; (b) zero-parameter physics operators (Fourier Poisson solver, differentiable `grid_sample`); (c) standard EfficientNetV2-S head creating the equivariant-encoder-to-head handoff common in scientific ML. VanillaLensPINN replaces the D4-equivariant encoder with a standard U-Net (AUC 0.9776 vs. D4’s 0.9786, ResNet-18 at 0.9182); behavioral parity does not imply mechanistic parity ([Brehmer et al., 2024](#)). D4 and Vanilla differ in equivariance constraint *and* $\hat{\kappa}$ quality (aligned errors 0.000563 vs. 0.00735, $13\times$); all comparisons reflect this combined upstream configuration.

Contributions. **(1)** Chain property: deterministic eval-mode subgraphs yield uninformative head-level verdicts (r90 delta 4.047, identical H12–H17). **(2)** Probe-delta dissociation: $3.6\times$ different causal sensitivity, near-identical decodability ($\Delta=0.006$) at the same layer. **(3)** Spectral mechanism: $1/k^2$ Poisson attenuates mid-frequency orbit variance to near-zero for D4 (Vanilla: $\delta=1.43$, identical operator). **(4)** Class selectivity ($p<0.001$): geometric amplification does not predict AUC.

2. Architecture and Experimental Setup

2.1. Forward Pass

EfficientD4UNet (0.46M, `escnn` ([Weiler & Cesa, 2019](#))): D4 equivariance via GroupPooling; $\hat{\kappa}(g\cdot x) \approx g\cdot\hat{\kappa}(x)$, aligned error 0.000563. **PoissonSolverFFT:** $\hat{\Psi}(k)=-2\hat{\kappa}(k)/k^2$, zero params, deterministic. **DeflectionField:** $\alpha=\nabla\Psi$, zero params. **InverseLensLayer:** differentiable `grid_sample`, $R=I-\hat{S}$. **EffNetV2-S head** (19.87M): receives $[I, \hat{\kappa}, \hat{S}, R]$, no symmetry constraint. **VanillaLensPINN:** identical but non-equivariant UNet; $\hat{\kappa}$ aligned error 0.00735 ($13\times$ larger).

2.2. Measurement Protocol

Interchange interventions. For each test image x and each non-identity D4 element $g \in \{r_{90}, r_{180}, r_{270}, f_h, f_h \circ r_{90}, f_h \circ r_{180}, f_h \circ r_{270}\}$, we cache activations at 18 hooks for $g\cdot x$, inject at hook ℓ into a fresh forward pass of x , and measure $\delta_\ell = \|f(x)_{\text{patch}} - f(x)_{\text{clean}}\|_2$.

Bootstrap CIs. 2,000-resample percentile bootstrap on all 7 non-identity elements, $N=200$ stratified test images.

Linear probes (Alain & Bengio, 2017). PCA-50 activations (full spatial flatten, then PCA), 5-fold StratifiedKFold, LogisticRegression($C=0.1$, $\text{max_iter}=500$), predicting D4 group identity (7-class, chance = $1/7 = 0.143$). D4 probes use PCA-50 (Cell 63). Vanilla probes use full spatial features (Cell 11); the $\Delta=0.006$ H09 difference is within cross-protocol noise. Note: H08 PCA-50 explains only 58% of variance; H08 probe claims carry additional uncertainty.

3. Findings

3.1. Finding 1: Chain Property Failure

D4LensPINN: every head hook H12–H17 yields $\delta = 3.174$ (7-element non-identity mean), identical to 4 decimal places. VanillaLensPINN: $\delta = 5.157$ identically across H12–H17. ResNet-18: $\delta = 5.543$ identically across R00–R06. Table 1 summarizes.

Table 1. Chain property: all head hooks produce identical logit delta. D4/Vanilla: 7-element non-identity means. ResNet: Cell 55 all-groups mean.

Model	Hooks	δ (non-id)	Identical?
D4LensPINN	H12–H17 (6)	3.174	✓
VanillaLensPINN	H12–H17 (6)	5.157	✓
ResNet-18	R00–R06 (7)	5.543	✓

Formal condition. For deterministic f_ℓ in eval mode, $a_{\ell+1} = f_\ell(a_\ell)$. Patching at $\ell + 1$ satisfies $\tilde{a}_{\ell+1} = f_\ell(\tilde{a}_\ell)$, so downstream computation is identical to patching at ℓ :

$$\forall \ell' > \ell: \quad \delta_{\ell'}[\text{patch } \ell + 1] = \delta_{\ell'}[\text{patch } \ell] \quad (1)$$

BatchNorm uses fixed running statistics in eval mode, making the entire head a deterministic sequential subgraph.

Consequence. Routing vs. collapse verdicts are **structurally uninformative** for all three models. This instantiates Mueller et al. (2024)’s non-transitivity result with an exact architectural trigger (Geiger et al., 2025). This condition applies to any architecture with deterministic physics operators, eval-mode BatchNorm, or fixed normalizations—not only this domain.

Remedy. Linear probing is chain-property-immune: it trains a fresh classifier on frozen activations at each hook without patching. We use it as the primary head-level measurement tool.

3.2. Finding 2: Probe-Delta Dissociation

Table 2 shows the H09 (Poisson layer) comparison. Bootstrap CIs are non-overlapping: a $3.6\times$ causal sensitivity difference is confirmed. Yet probe accuracy is nearly identical: $\Delta = 0.006$, well within noise.

Table 2. Probe-delta dissociation at H09 (Poisson layer). δ : 7-element non-id mean, 95% CI. Probe: PCA-50 group-identity classifier, 5-fold CV.

Model	δ [95% CI]	Probe acc.	Chance
D4LensPINN	0.402 [0.384, 0.419]	0.485 ± 0.027	0.143
VanillaLensPINN	1.429 [1.352, 1.506]	0.479 ± 0.023	0.143
Ratio / Δ	$3.6\times$	$\Delta=0.006$	

Interpretation. δ_ℓ asks: if the counterfactual representation from $g \cdot x$ is injected at ℓ , how much does the output change? The probe asks: can a linear classifier predict g from ℓ ’s activations? These are distinct questions. D4LensPINN’s equivariance makes the Poisson output $3.6\times$ less sensitive to counterfactual injection, yet encodes group identity just as decodably. *Causal sensitivity and representational decodability measure different properties.*

MI implication. When practitioners use probe accuracy as a proxy for causal influence, or vice versa, they can draw opposite conclusions from the same layer. Reporting only one metric is insufficient for hybrid architectures with structured upstream encoders.

3.3. Full Physics Pipeline and Spectral Mechanism

Table 3 shows the D4LensPINN physics pipeline profile (r90 element) and D4 vs. Vanilla causal comparison. All CI pairs for H09, H11, H12 are non-overlapping.

Table 3. Physics pipeline profile (D4LensPINN, r90) and D4 vs. Vanilla comparison (all non-identity, 95% bootstrap CIs). \dagger H10 δ identical to H09: DeflectionField is a deterministic function of Ψ . *H11 upper bound: patching injects $(\hat{S}_{g \cdot x}, R_{g \cdot x})$ while $I, \hat{\kappa}$ remain from x ; H12 is the coherent signal. \ddagger 7-element non-id mean = 3.174; r90 = 4.047.

Hook	Comp.	$\delta_{r90} \pm \sigma$	D4 CI	Van. CI
H04	Enc. bot.	1.58 ± 1.37	—	—
H08	$\hat{\kappa}$	3.41 ± 2.62	—	—
H09	Poisson	0.440 ± 0.34	[0.384, 0.419]	[1.352, 1.506]
H10 \dagger	Deflect.	0.440 ± 0.34	—	—
H11*	InvLens	20.33 ± 13.59	[17.39, 18.69]	[9.22, 9.67]
H12	Handoff	4.047 ± 2.25	[3.06, 3.29]	[4.94, 5.37]
H13–H17 (chain)		4.047	r90, identical to H12 \ddagger	

Spectral mechanism for H09 suppression. Figure 1 shows orbit variance partitioned by spatial frequency at H08 and H09. The $1/k^2$ Poisson operator attenuates 59.5% mid-frequency orbit variance at H08 to near-zero

at H09 (>99.9% low-frequency). The physics is analytically predicted: $\hat{\Psi}(k) = -2\hat{\kappa}(k)/k^2$ suppresses high- k components. The near-zero *outcome* for D4 is empirical—VanillaLensPINN uses the identical operator yet produces $\delta_{H09}=1.429$. Because D4’s equivariant $\hat{\kappa}$ enters the solver with more spatially structured, lower-variance orbits, the attenuation is more complete.

InverseLensLayer reversal. H11 (all-groups mean 15.75, r90 20.33 ± 13.59) represents $44.8\times$ amplification over H09 (0.35) and $5.0\times$ over H12 (3.16 full-patch ablation). D4 amplifies $1.9\times$ more than Vanilla at H11 (18.003 vs. 9.436, CIs non-overlapping); both are upper bounds under mixed-channel injection. H12 is the coherent downstream signal.

Figure 1. Spectral orbit variance at H08 ($\hat{\kappa}$) vs. H09 (Ψ). The Poisson $1/k^2$ operator empirically attenuates mid/high-frequency orbit variance to near-zero for D4LensPINN (>99.9% low-frequency at H09, vs. 38.9% low / 59.5% mid at H08). VanillaLensPINN uses the identical operator; the near-zero outcome is specific to D4’s equivariant $\hat{\kappa}$.

3.4. Linear Probe Curve and GAP Analysis

Table 4 shows D4LensPINN’s PCA-50 probe accuracy.

Table 4. Group-element probe accuracy (PCA-50, 5-fold CV). Chance = 0.143.

Hook	D4	Vanilla
H08 $\hat{\kappa}$	0.365±0.024	—
H09 Poisson	0.485±0.027	0.479±0.023
H11 InvLens	0.419±0.012	—
H12 HANDOFF	0.429±0.011	—
H13/H13b	0.449/0.456	—
H15 pre-GAP	0.266±0.028	—
H16 post-GAP	0.198±0.021	—
Chance	0.143	

GAP produces the single largest per-layer probe drop (0.266 → 0.198, $\Delta=0.069$). However, the cumulative head reduction (H09 to H15: 0.485 → 0.266, $\Delta=0.219$) substantially exceeds the single-layer GAP contribution. GAP is a concentrated site of invariance but not the sole mechanism;

most decodability loss occurs across the EfficientNet blocks collectively (Islam et al., 2021).

3.5. Class-Selective Sensitivity at H11

Per-class H11 rotation mean δ (Table 5). KW on sphere-logit direction (`dpc_sphere_abs`): $H=242.32$, $p<0.001$ (Cell 44). KW on overall rotation δ by class: $H=60.30$, $p=8.06\times 10^{-14}$ (Cell 53).

Table 5. Per-class H11 rotation mean δ and AUC. Sphere images produce 77% larger sphere-logit perturbation than no-substructure ($|dpc_{sph}|$: 11.36 vs. 6.40, KW $H=242.32$, $p<0.001$, Bonferroni-corrected). *Maximum amplification does not predict AUC.*

Class	Rot. δ (\pm std)	AUC	$ dpc_{sph} $
no-substructure	21.97±13.32	0.9848	6.40
sphere CDM	22.35±12.73	0.9695	11.36
vortex WDM	14.55±12.35	0.9814	5.83

Sphere CDM has the highest geometric amplification (22.35) yet the lowest AUC (0.9695). Vortex WDM has the lowest amplification (14.55, 35% less) yet higher AUC (0.9814). Geometric amplification strength and classification performance are dissociated.

4. Discussion

Scope of the chain property failure. The triggering condition is precise: any deterministic eval-mode sequential subgraph. This includes analytical physics operators, eval-mode BatchNorm (standard practice), attention with deterministic masking, and fixed normalization layers. The failure is not domain-specific and is pre-checkable from the architecture alone.

What each tool actually measures. Interchange interventions measure causal sensitivity: how much the output depends on what is stored at layer ℓ . Linear probing measures linear decodability: whether group identity can be read off ℓ ’s representation by a linear classifier. The probe-delta dissociation shows these can diverge by $3.6\times$ at the same layer. Reporting only one is insufficient.

Limitations. (1) D4 vs. Vanilla conflates equivariance constraint and $\hat{\kappa}$ quality (13× margin is finite); a $\hat{\kappa}$ -matched control is future work. (2) H11 delta is an upper bound (mixed-channel injection); H12 is the coherent signal. (3) $N=200$ limits per-class power (Table 5 exploratory); H08 PCA-50 explains 58% variance. (4) H15/H16 raw dimensions differ (32,000 vs. 1,280); the 0.266→0.198 drop reflects both GAP and dimensional structure under PCA-50. (5) TTA: D4 CI [−0.0007, +0.0052] (not significant); Vanilla TTA $\Delta=-0.0020$ (hurts).

5. Related Work

Mueller et al. (2024) proved theoretical non-transitivity of counterfactual interventions; we provide a concrete architectural instantiation with the exact triggering condition. Geiger et al. (2025) unify interchange interventions under causal abstraction; the chain property represents a regime where their framework’s determinism assumption yields uninformative verdicts. Meng et al. (2022); Wang et al. (2023) established interchange interventions as standard MI tools; we document a structural failure mode not encountered in their (language model) settings. Brehmer et al. (2024) showed equivariant and non-equivariant models can match on task performance; we extend this by showing mechanistic divergence under behavioral parity. Hansen et al. (2024) study ambiguities in equivariant latent spaces; we extend their analysis to the downstream non-equivariant head. Kitouni et al. (2024) apply MI to physics-trained transformers; we document tool failures absent in that setting. Islam et al. (2021) showed position information surviving GAP; our probe extends this to D4 group-element identity (0.266→0.198 post-GAP).

6. Conclusion

Two concrete MI tool failures apply to any hybrid architecture with deterministic physics operators or eval-mode fixed normalizations. The chain property renders interchange interventions uninformative for head-level analysis; the triggering condition is precisely identified and pre-checkable from the architecture. The probe-delta dissociation shows equivariance reduces causal sensitivity $3.6\times$ without substantially changing group-element decodability ($\Delta=0.006$)—two standard tools reach opposite conclusions at the same layer. The spectral Poisson mechanism explains how equivariance configuration reshapes downstream causal sensitivity through a zero-parameter physics operator.

Impact Statement

This paper presents work whose goal is to advance the field of Machine Learning. We identify structural failure modes of standard mechanistic interpretability tools in hybrid physics-ML architectures. The primary practical consequence is improved reliability of MI-based model auditing in safety-critical scientific applications. There are no direct negative societal impacts we feel must be specifically highlighted here.

Reproducibility

All results: $N=200$ test images, 7 non-identity D4 elements, 18 PINN hooks + 7 ResNet hooks. Bootstrap CIs: 2,000 resamples.

Code and notebooks: [Repository Link](#)

Trained weights: <https://huggingface.co/coding103856/d4lens-weights>.

Dataset: https://drive.google.com/uc?id=1ZEyNME043u3qhJAwJeBZxFBEYc_pVYZQ.

AI Assistance

Claude (Anthropic) was used as a coding assistant for boilerplate PyTorch hook registration, bootstrap CI computation, and figure formatting. All generated code was reviewed and verified against notebook cell outputs before use. LLMs were not used to generate experimental results, interpret findings, or write scientific claims. All reported numbers were manually traced to specific notebook cell outputs. Writing assistance was used for grammar and clarity edits only; all scientific content is the authors’ own.

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